

THE ROLE OF LEGAL CONSCIOUSNESS AND LEGAL CULTURE IN RAISING YOUTH SPIRITUALITY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11401741>

Annotation. This article describes the issues of the formation of legal consciousness and legal culture in the family, the role of the family in society and the influence of the environment in the family on the upbringing of children, and the main factors of juvenile delinquency.

Keywords: family, spirituality, authentic consciousness, legal culture, obedience to the law, respect for the law, upbringing of children, legal thinking, juvenile delinquency.

Аннотация. Ушбу мақолада оилада ҳуқуқий онг ва ҳуқуқий маданиятнинг шаклланиши, жамиятда оиланинг тутган ўрни ва оиладаги муҳитнинг фарзанд тарбиясига таъсири ҳамда вояга етмаган шахслар жиноятчилигининг асосий омиллари тўғрисидаги масалалар баён этилган.

Калит сўзлар: оила, маънавият, ҳуқуқий онг, ҳуқуқий маданият, қонунга итоат, қонунга ҳурмат, фарзанд тарбияси, ҳуқуқий тафаккур, вояга етмаганлар жиноятчилиги.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются вопросы формирования правосознания и правовой культуры в семье, роль семьи в обществе и влияние окружения в семье на воспитание детей, а также основные факторы преступности несовершеннолетних.

Ключевые слова: семья, духовность, аутентичное сознание, правовая культура, законопослушание, уважение к закону, воспитание детей, правовое мышление, преступность несовершеннолетних.

Since ancient times, our people have recognized the family as sacred and valued it. This is one of the highest traditions of the Uzbek people that have been passed down to generations.

In our country, serious attention has been paid to the development of family relations, which are considered an important part of society, to establish a stable environment in the family, to improve its legal foundations, and to prevent crimes that may be committed in the family.

Chapter XIV of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which is our main law, is dedicated to family issues. In particular, it states that the family is under state protection, marriage equality, parents' responsibility for their children until they reach adulthood, and society's care for minors [1].

Respect for the law is one of the most necessary needs that is instilled and strengthened in the mind of every person from childhood. Respect and obedience to the law is the basis of legal consciousness and legal culture. A person should obey the laws not just blindly, but consciously. For this, it is necessary to ensure high level of legal awareness and legal culture in the society.

Ensuring legal awareness and legal culture starts with the family, which is the main link of the society. In order to form legal consciousness and legal culture in the family, first of all, each member of the family should know their rights and duties perfectly and be able to protect their rights.

Disputes arising between spouses, brothers, sisters and children in the family mainly indicate insufficient legal awareness and legal culture.

Various conflicts, divorces and negative atmosphere in the family are the reason for the increase of juvenile delinquency.

This requires increased attention to the prevention of juvenile delinquency in society. For this, first of all, many measures are being implemented to ensure high level of legal awareness and legal culture in the family of minors.

We know that high level of legal awareness and legal culture is important in crime prevention. For this purpose, official state and public organizations and law enforcement agencies should carry out educational, moral and educational activities based on mutual cooperation.

Parents should be especially careful with their children during their teenage years. Adolescence in children lasts from approximately 11-12 to 14-16 years. It is during this period that crime among minors is observed more often.

The formation of a person as a person first of all begins with the family. This is strongly influenced by the environment, conditions and attitudes of the family. A chaotic lifestyle, poor conditions and negative attitudes in the family can cause a child to become a criminal. In order to prevent this, it is necessary to have a positive attitude towards the child as soon as it is born, to prevent conflicts arising in the family, and parents should form legal thinking in their children.

The spirituality of a person is first formed in the family. Spirituality is the strength of a person, society, nation, and state. Where there is no spirituality there can never be happiness.

The better a person is brought up in the family, the more positive qualities the parents teach, the more healthy the environment is for the spiritual formation of a person, the more spiritually healthy, mature children will always emerge from this family [2.165].

From a criminological point of view, the factors affecting the negative moral formation of a person in the family can be divided into two groups. The first group includes objective factors, i.e. long-term illness of the parents, incomplete family, financial difficulties, culture of some parents, low level of education, absence or lack of time for parenting, housing and poor household conditions and others. These objective factors can influence the formation of certain negative moral characteristics in a person [2-165]. For example, a long-term illness of a parent with an underage child may cause various stress conditions to be observed in the underage child. In this case, the child misses school to take care of his sick parents, as a result of which he lags behind in education, the level of spirituality and culture is low, and he is unable to find a decent job in order to earn money for the family's lack and treatment of his parents, and causes him to commit various crimes.

Subjective factors can be included in the second group of negative moral formation of a person. Subjective factors include family members encouraging each other to engage in antisocial behavior, i.e. alcoholism, robbery, theft, prostitution and other social activities, negatively affecting the upbringing of children through their illegal actions, even if they do not directly encourage these situations, unhealthy environment in the family, quarrels, conflicts, lack of legal awareness and legal culture in the family as a result of parents' disdain for laws.

In some families, parents quarrel in front of their children and abuse each other with all sorts of unspiritual words. These behaviors have a negative impact on the child's upbringing, mind and spiritual views. As a result of this, as they say, "What a bird sees in its nest, what it sees in its

nest", minor children get used to insulting their friends on the street, at school and in other places with various unethical words.

Regular conflicts in the family make minors, who are just entering adulthood, depressed and nervous. As a result, juvenile delinquency in the society increases sharply. Currently, criminological studies show that the main cause of crimes among minors is an unhealthy environment in the family [2-168].

In addition to the above, upbringing in the family has a great impact on the spirituality of children. Excessive caressing or humiliating a child in the family, not controlling their behavior and not knowing what kind of people they are communicating with and making friends prevents minor children from becoming mentally and physically mature individuals. As a result, the number of mentally immature people in our society is increasing, which causes the nation to become spiritually poor.

In order to establish legal awareness and legal culture in the family and society, it is necessary to carry out the following activities:

Firstly, improving the system of legal education and upbringing in the family;

Second, to ensure that all government bodies, officials and citizens obey and respect the law;

Thirdly, to develop various measures to increase the legal literacy of citizens, as well as each family member;

Fourthly, it is desirable to establish that the environment in each family is regularly studied and controlled by citizens' self-management bodies and prevention inspectors. Also, it is important to create a strong family, ensure family stability, and prepare young people for family life, not only by forming the worldview of young people, but also by carrying out various campaigning and promotion activities among adults and parents, and increasing the literacy of parents in the field of family management. Well, a reasonable question arises as to how and where the practical work that needs to be carried out in this direction should be carried out to be effective.

Families are concentrated in neighborhoods. Currently in our country for 10 thousand nearby neighborhoods are operating. In recent years, the head of state and our government have implemented a number of practical and effective measures to develop the neighborhood institution on the basis of comprehensive reforms, increase its legal status and increase its powers.

Children are brought up in the families of the neighborhood. A number of planned activities aimed at the development of spiritual education in the family are being carried out at the community gatherings. It is in the provision of such activities that the implementation of the following activities can give effective results: help in the implementation of activities aimed at increasing the legal, moral, moral and physiological knowledge of parents on raising the young generation participating in demonstrations and lectures, working with parents who have a negative impact on child upbringing, preventing various negative situations in the neighborhood (criminality, especially crimes among women and young people, troubled families, drug addiction, alcoholism, early marriage of underage girls) , to ensure the strengthening and stability of families, to provide assistance to parents in mastering the science of raising children, to ensure a healthy psychological environment in the family, to form a sense of concern for the health of family members in families, and legal, to help increase their spiritual, moral and physiological knowledge.

In conclusion, it can be said that the family is the center of legal consciousness and legal culture. Obedience and respect for the law begins with the family. Therefore, as soon as a child is born, legal consciousness and legal culture are formed in this place. First of all, we need to create a healthy environment in the family in order for our children to grow up to be mentally and physically mature people.

A healthy environment in the family prevents minor children from entering the street of crime and has a great impact on their spiritual formation. As President Shavkat Miromovich Mirziyoyev noted, "Family is a small homeland, if the family is peaceful and happy, the Motherland will be peaceful" [3].

It is the main duty of parents in every family to pay serious attention to the education of children in the family, which is considered a small part of the society, to prevent them from entering the street of crime and to educate them as a person who serves the Motherland.

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